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Integrated Use of Remote Sensing and Seismological Data for Mapping Earthquake-Induced Landslides in Norway

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Norway's topography, marked by steep slopes and broad valleys, combined with the abundant water resources and effects of climate change, makes it particularly vulnerable to landslide processes. Fluctuations in water table levels, primarily caused by seasonal runoffs, are widely recognized as the most common triggers of landslides in Norway. However, studies suggest that earthquakes, though less frequent, also play a significant role in initiating these events. Furthermore, even though the intraplate seismicity of Norway results in generally lower magnitude earthquakes, recent research has expanded the understanding of landslide triggers in Norway, showing evidence of earthquake-induced landslides (EQIL). This study aims to improve understanding of earthquakes' potential to trigger landslides in Norway. For selected, recent larger ($M > 3.5$) earthquakes, we systematically search for potentially triggered landslides in Sentinel-2 imagery. To define the precise timing of landslide events and verify their connection to seismic activity, we examine seismological databases for records from the nearest seismic stations. This allows us to precisely pinpoint the timing of landslides detected via optical satellite imagery, overcoming challenges such as cloud coverage and limited temporal resolution. Our approach aims to differentiate various landslide triggering mechanisms (e.g., precipitation versus earthquakes) and to establish the thresholds for magnitude and distance relevant to EQILs. The preliminary findings presented here aim to shed light on the dynamics of cascading earthquake-landslide events in Norway, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of these complex natural processes.

